

Research Article

The Development of Smart Aero Tools Cleansing

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Abstract: Tool cleanliness in aircraft maintenance plays a crucial role in ensuring safety, operational efficiency, and compliance with aviation regulations. Traditional manual cleaning methods are time-consuming, inconsistent, and expose workers to health hazards. This research presents the development of the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device, an automated solution designed to clean and dry aircraft maintenance tools using a 360-degree water spray system, an exhaust drying fan, and Arduino Uno-based automation. The project aims to reduce tool downtime, enhance workplace safety, and promote consistency in tool maintenance. Built from durable acrylic materials and integrated with programmable logic and safety features, the device operates within a 3.5-minute wash and 2-minute dry cycle, using a moderately alkaline detergent. A user interface with push buttons and a Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) allows operators to monitor and control the process with ease. The device's compact size and mobile structure make it ideal for workshops and training environments. Survey results from aviation students and lecturers revealed a strong interest in the solution and acknowledged the current limitations of manual cleaning. The prototype successfully demonstrated improved tool hygiene, time efficiency, and user safety. With low production costs and customisation potential, the device holds strong commercialisation potential in aviation and other industrial sectors requiring standardised tool cleanliness.

Keywords: aircraft maintenance; tool cleaning; aviation safety; tool hygiene; Arduino system

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the aviation industry, the cleanliness and maintenance of tools used by aircraft technicians are essential for ensuring flight safety, operational efficiency, and compliance with regulatory standards. Poorly maintained or contaminated tools may lead to Foreign Object Damage (FOD), which can compromise aircraft systems and jeopardise safety (Schenk et al., 2020). According to the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), FOD costs the aviation industry billions annually due to delays, damage, and safety violations. Despite the availability of advanced maintenance procedures, the cleaning of tools in many aviation facilities remains a largely manual task, prone to inconsistencies, prolonged cleaning times, and risks of chemical exposure for workers (Fernandes et al., 2025). These limitations highlight the urgent need for a reliable and standardised method of tool hygiene in aviation environments.

Manual cleaning not only varies in effectiveness depending on the user's technique and level of attention but also exposes technicians to potential hazards such as chemical burns, repetitive strain injuries, and contact with contaminated tools (Schenk et al., 2020). While ultrasonic and steam-cleaning

systems are available in other industrial sectors, these solutions are often expensive, require specialised handling, and are not designed specifically for small-scale aviation toolkits (Kohli, 2019). Furthermore, many aviation Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions and maintenance workshops lack the financial resources and space to accommodate such industrial-grade systems. Therefore, there is a growing interest in low-cost, user-friendly, and mobile solutions that can ensure consistent cleaning outcomes without compromising safety.

The Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device was developed as an innovative response to these challenges. It is designed to automate the cleaning and drying process using programmable electronics (Arduino Uno) and mechanical systems, such as a 360-degree water sprinkler and exhaust drying fan, all housed in a compact acrylic body. This project aligns with the global trend toward smart workshop practices, Industry 4.0 integration, and sustainability in engineering education (Goon et al., 2019). The integration of affordable automation into routine maintenance tasks not only enhances the effectiveness and safety of tool hygiene but also supports the development of engineering competencies among students and technicians. The project thus serves both a practical industrial need and an educational purpose.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device followed a systematic engineering design process comprising problem identification, data collection, conceptual design, component selection, system integration, and final fabrication. The project began with the distribution of a structured questionnaire aimed at understanding the challenges faced by aircraft maintenance technicians and students regarding manual tool cleaning practices. The survey was completed by 30 respondents, including lecturers and students from Politeknik Banting Selangor’s Aircraft Maintenance program. The responses revealed that 80% of users experienced difficulties due to inconsistent manual cleaning and tool contamination, while 76.7% expressed interest in an automated solution that could improve efficiency and safety in maintenance environments.

Based on the survey findings, the design team generated three conceptual designs. Each concept was evaluated using a morphological chart and Pugh Matrix, with criteria including cost, size, ease of fabrication, safety, and functionality. After evaluating the pros and cons of each concept, the most feasible design was selected. This final concept featured a 360-degree water spray system, drying mechanism using an exhaust fan, and an Arduino-controlled automation cycle. Technical drawings were produced using computer-aided design (CAD) software to detail the layout, dimensions, and integration of mechanical, electrical, and electronic components. **Figure 1** below illustrated the design of smart aero tools cleansing device using CAD.

Figure 1. Design of a smart aero tools cleansing device

The smart aero tools cleansing device's prototype was constructed using acrylic sheets for the main body, chosen for their durability, transparency, and ease of assembly. Internally, a submersible brushless water pump was installed to power the rotating sprinkler system, which distributed detergent and water across the tools. An alternate current (AC-powered) exhaust fan was fitted to provide the drying function. The system was automated using an Arduino Uno microcontroller programmed to operate a 3.5-minute washing cycle followed by a 2-minute drying cycle. A user interface consisting of push buttons, an I2C LCD display, and an emergency stop button was integrated to enhance usability and safety. The final assembly involved mechanical fabrication (cutting, fitting, and joining acrylic components), electrical wiring, Arduino programming, and system testing to ensure the functionality and safety of the device.

3. FINDINGS

The prototype was successfully developed and tested, demonstrating its ability to automate both the cleaning and drying processes for aviation hand tools. The device operates using an Arduino Uno microcontroller that controls a 360-degree sprinkler for washing and an exhaust fan for drying, following a programmed cycle of 3.5 minutes for cleaning and 2 minutes for drying. During functional testing, the device consistently cleaned multiple tools within a single cycle, using moderate amounts of water and detergent. The internal spray system delivered even coverage across all tool surfaces, effectively removing grease and contaminants. The exhaust fan component successfully eliminated residual moisture, ensuring that tools were dry and ready for reuse or storage without requiring manual wiping.

User testing and survey responses supported the effectiveness and necessity of the device. A total of 30 respondents, including lecturers and students from the aircraft maintenance program, participated in a feedback session. The data showed that 80% had previously experienced challenges with manually cleaned tools, while 76.7% believed that an automated tool cleaning system would improve safety and efficiency in maintenance environments. Additionally, users praised the compact size, portability, and ease of use provided by the LCD screen and push-button interface. Cost-wise, the total fabrication cost of the prototype was kept under RM250, meeting the project's goal of affordability. The results clearly indicate that the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device is both functionally viable and highly relevant to its intended user base in aviation workshops and TVET institutions.

4. DISCUSSION

The successful development and testing of the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device reflect the effectiveness of integrating low-cost automation into maintenance practices, particularly in aviation settings. By automating the cleaning and drying processes, the device addresses key limitations of manual tool maintenance, including time inefficiency, inconsistency, and safety hazards. Similar efforts in automating maintenance tasks have demonstrated improved operational efficiency and worker safety in technical fields, particularly when using microcontroller-based systems like Arduino (Sivaganesh et al., 2024). The integration of an Arduino Uno allowed for flexible programming of wash and dry cycles, enhancing user control and system reliability. Compared to existing industrial-grade cleaning systems such as ultrasonic or steam-based units, which can be expensive and less accessible the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device offers a cost-effective alternative tailored for small-scale aviation workshops and educational environments (Umar et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the positive user feedback from students and lecturers reinforces the relevance and practicality of the device. Respondents highlighted its ease of use, safety features, and suitability for routine maintenance, aligning with previous research that emphasizes the importance of human-centred design in engineering education tools. The project's compact and portable structure enhances its deployment across various maintenance stations, while its transparent acrylic casing allows for visibility and inspection during operation, an important feature in technical training environments. Although the device met its intended objectives, opportunities remain for improvement. For instance, incorporating a water recycling system as shown in **Figure 2** or sensor-based automation could further improve its sustainability and efficiency. This aligns with broader trends in green engineering and sustainable TVET practices, where energy and resource efficient systems are increasingly (Ibrahim & Rahim, 2024). Moving forward, these improvements could increase the device's scalability and commercialisation potential across diverse technical sectors.

Figure 2. Fabricated of Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device controlled by Arduino UNO

5. CONCLUSION

The development of the Smart Aero Tools Cleansing Device has demonstrated a practical and innovative solution to enhance tool cleanliness and safety in aircraft maintenance operations. By automating the cleaning and drying processes, the device effectively addresses key issues associated with manual methods, including time inefficiency, inconsistent results, and occupational hazards. The integration of Arduino-based control, a 360-degree water spray, and a drying fan ensures a reliable, safe, and user-friendly solution suitable for both aviation workshops and educational environments. Positive outcomes from prototype testing and user feedback confirm that the device meets its intended goals in functionality, safety, and relevance to aviation maintenance practices. Moreover, this project aligns with several United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) by promoting safer and more efficient workplace practices, SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) through the application of low-cost automation in technical operations, and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) by encouraging efficient use of resources such as water and energy. The project's emphasis on integrating engineering design,

sustainability, and digitalisation also contributes to improved learning experiences within TVET institutions. Future improvements, such as incorporating water recycling systems, sensor-based automation, and IoT connectivity, can further enhance the device's environmental performance and scalability, reinforcing its role as a sustainable and forward-thinking innovation in the field of aircraft maintenance.

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